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**EFFECTS OF TRAINING ON EMPLOYEES' PERFORMANCE IN THE PARLIAMENT OF
GHANA**

Michael Ampadu¹, Erika Varga², Emese Bruder³

*1Msc student, 2PhD, associate professor, 3PhD, assistant professor 1,2,3Hungarian University of
Agriculture and Life Sciences, Formerly Szent Istvan University*

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ABSTRACT

Training is regarded as the mainstream of any organization because the success of an organization to achieve its objectives and goals heavily and highly depends on its workforce. The concentration was based on staffs who have been working in various departments of the Parliament of Ghana after having been trained for the first time and various methods used in training. This study employed a quota sampling technique to draw a sample of 133 employees from a population of 200 staff in four (4) departments; Research (R), Protocol (P), Human Resource (HR), ICT (I), through self-administered questionnaire. The purpose of the study was to examine the impact of training on employees' performance, employees' motivation, and job-satisfaction in the parliament of Ghana. The findings of the study generally revealed that training not only increases employees' performance but also positively affects employees' motivation and job satisfaction among parliamentary staff in Ghana. Therefore, it is recommended that the parliament of Ghana should regularly organize annual training sessions among staff to get themselves acquainted with the new training methods and ideas to sharpen the employees' skills, knowledge, and abilities to capacitate them to cope with the ever-changing working environment and uncertain conditions and improve their performance, motivation, and job satisfaction.

Keywords: training, employee performance, job satisfaction, motivation, Parliament of Ghana

INTRODUCTION

As part of their human resource development strategy, most of the firms invest in building and improving the skills of their workforce to do their job as desired and cope with the uncertain conditions they may face in the future. As an asset that cannot be imitated by the competition, companies put great emphasis on achieving high levels of employee performance to gain a resource advantage. To do so, companies employ improvement initiatives. These initiatives aim to address waste in manufacturing processes and business design, reducing the non-value adding operation and increasing performance that could improve profits. A key aspect of these programs is employee performance improvement plans that are partly vested in training. However, the necessary investments and results are often unexpected. When management offers training programs in an

organization, the employees bring out their best efforts to achieve organizational goals, which translates to high performance of their job.

There are several factors effecting employee performance which emanates from the internal and external environment of the organization. To date, literature has established that research is focused on measuring a specific aspect of it such as motivation or training. Further to this, there is a high level of uncertainty when it comes to human behavior that complicates further any attempt to predict the outcome of such initiatives. Without proper training, neither new nor current employees receive the information and develop the skill sets necessary for accomplishing their tasks at their maximum potential. Employees who undergo proper training tend to keep their jobs longer than those who do not. Sahoo, et al. (2010) showed that employee who is loyal to his or her job and career has less intention to take a leave or quit, tends to feel secured about the job, and has higher intrinsic motivation.

In the recent and changing organizational environments various organizations make significant efforts to ensure organizational commitment and job satisfaction among their employees for the purpose of maintaining them and improving their productivity. Organizational engagement has been widely accepted to be advantageous for both the organization and its employees as it can reinforce the feelings of belongingness, job security, career development, improved compensation, and higher intrinsic rewards (Azeem & Akhtar, 2014). Rochon (2014) regarded teamwork as a key success factor for employee performance and described it as a group of employees who work together to achieve a certain goal. In other words, teamwork is a collaborative and shared activity that is directed towards accomplishing desired objective.

Training is a necessity at the workplace. Without it, employees do not have a firm grasp on their responsibilities or duties. Employee training refers to programs that provide workers with information, new skills, or professional development opportunities in executing their duties efficiently. The idea of training has become important and known to people in human resources due to its good measures with employee performance (Kiweewa & Asiimwe, 2014). Training is also a form of capacity building in any institution that is undertaken to improve staff performance and to enable an institution to meet her objectives (Tahir et al., 2014).

Training programs are basically in two forms; that is 'on the job' and 'off the job' trainings (Sultan et al., 2012). According to Sultan et al. (2012), employees who take part in 'on the job' training are said to be great performers as compared to those who take part in 'off the job' training. This is as a result to the vast job experience, which escalate in both skills and knowledge. However, a

complementary relationship was found between receiving ‘on the job’ training and receiving ‘off the job’ training. Previous studies prove that there is a strong positive correlation between training and employee performance. For example, Elnaga & Imran (2013) established that training is one of the vital and sensitive human resource management. Training is also a form of activity, which is planned, systematic and its results promote the level of skills and knowledge that are necessary to perform work effectively (Sultana et al., 2012). Training is mainly concerned with the increase and upgrade of the skills and knowledge of the employees that add up to job performance (Azeem et al. 2013). Training is one way of improving an individual’s productivity. In the training process, employees gain technical skills, interpersonal skills, and solid knowledge to perform their jobs efficiently and effectively at the workplace and lack of ongoing training programs leads to lower performance of employees (Nawaz et al., 2014).

Training not only helps the capabilities of the employee but hone their thinking ability and creativity to take better decision in time and in more productive manner (Elnaga & Imran, 2013). Training also makes employees interact with the customer in an effective manner and respond to their complaints in a timely manner (Amin et al., 2013). Therefore, to prepare workers to do their job as desired, organizations provide training to enhance their employees’ potential and capability (Kiweewa & Asiimwe, 2014). Most of the organization, by applying long-term planning, invest in building new skills, knowledge and changing the behaviors of their workforce enabling them to cope with the uncertainties that they may encounter in future, thus enhancing employee performance (Elnaga & Imran, 2013). In one of the accounting related scholarly works by Bananuka, et al. (2017) it was realized that when employees are not motivated to work and not given support to further their careers, it is perceived as a challenge by internal auditors, and this influences their performance. Bananuka et al. (2017) further documents that once internal auditors are not trained, it is perceived as a problem to the internal audit and these problems have a negative impact on their role performance. For example, Elnaga & Imran (2013) established that training is one of the vital and sensitive human resource management practices that positively affects the quality of the employee’s knowledge and skills, and this brings in higher employee performance on the job.

Employee Performance has been conceptualized in different ways, for example, according to Mensah (2015), it is the positive attitude held by the employees toward the organization and its values. The level of employee performance is highly determined by the level of commitment an employee has toward their organization and its values (Selvarasu & Sastry, 2014). An employee is aware of business context and works with colleagues to improve performance within the job for

the benefit of the organization (Ologbo & Sofian, 2013). According to Mensah (2015), performance is distinguished by energy, absorption, involvement, efficacy, vigor, dedication, enthusiasm, and a positive state, which are described as catalysts for employee performance. According to Shantz, et al. (2013), employees' performance has a positive attitude and have work-related state of mind characterized by vigor, dedication, and absorption and these make the employees psychologically present at work, which minimizes their possibility to do work related mistakes and errors. Gichohi (2014) explains that there is positive correlation and relationship between employee engagement and employee performance through increased commitment and this is because engaged employees experience positive emotions which broaden their thinking, leading them to become more attentive and absorbed in their work. (Shantz et al., 2013).

Motivation is very important in influencing the employees to accomplish individual as well as the organizational goals. This inner drive motivates the employees to form and exhibit the purposive behavior to achieve specific, unmet needs. This little encouragement on the part of organization enables them to accomplish their goals efficiently by acknowledging employees on their work and effort, providing them good work environment, considering their needs, and forming pleasant job design. Motivation increases performance. The system of the rewards and promotions regarding employee motivation is an important tool that management should consider directing and channel the employee's motivation on their desired scheme. The system of rewards and promotions comprise of all components in the organization, which include decision- making activities involved in allocating benefits and compensation to the employees for their contribution to the organization (Prateepkanth, 2011). The purpose of rewards and promotions is to provide a systematic approach for delivering positive consequences and attract people to join the organization and ultimately be motivated to deliver higher level of performance (Pratheepkanth, 2011). Employees perform when they are rewarded and when they exceed the expectation and limits and surpass the target to motivate them, they should be immediately rewarded. The practices of quick reward on performance will generate self-motivation and set higher standards by employees themselves as they will take the tasks positively and put all efforts to achieve targets. The system of rewards in the organization should be properly designed and implemented to reinforce positive behavior, which will directly impart positivity on employees' performance (Njanja et al., 2013).

Kinicki & Kreitner (2015) indicates other scholars in the literature measured job satisfaction in terms of need fulfillment, discrepancies, value attainment, equity and dispositional or genetic components models. According to Ocen et al. (2017), the literature measured job satisfaction in terms of extrinsic and intrinsic job-related factors. On the one hand, extrinsic factors include all the

external factors, which may satisfy employees such as communication style, supervisor cooperation, pay and working conditions. Also, intrinsic factors may comprise things like the type of work the employees perform and the duties considered by the employees in an organization.

There exists a link between employee training and job satisfaction. According to Sajuyigbe and Amusat (2015) employee training improves the satisfaction about their jobs. Siebern (2014) and Owens (2014) found that training and job satisfaction are positively correlated and that those employees who are offered training by their organizations are more gratified than those who do not receive such training. These results were also supported by Adesola et al., (2013) which confirms that staff training has a positive impact on job satisfaction among bank employees in Nigeria. These views were also supported by Owusu (2015) who argued that training reduces employees' frustration derived from work demands, which they may not be familiar with or aware of. Furthermore, Ruth & Esther (2013) argued that extensively trained employees are satisfied with their jobs, which, in turn make them satisfy the needs of their customers. Consequently, such employees become committed to their organizations, attend work, stay with an organization, arrive at work on time, perform well and engage in forms of behavior that are helpful to the organization. Job satisfaction as one of the most researched work-related variables has been shown to negatively influence undesirable employee behavior, such as absenteeism and turnover intentions. Managers struggled to understand how they could minimize turnover, and this generally led them back to the need to understand their employees' perceptions of satisfaction. Derakhshandeh and Mohammad Khani (2016) conducted research entitled "The relationship between job satisfactions with the performance of employees of the social security organization of the Markazi Province". The method of this research is survey and the statistical population of the study consisted of employees of the social security organization of the Markazi province, which were 437 people in 2015. Using Cochran formula, 136 of them were selected as random stratified random sampling method. The data collection tool was Susan's (2005) five-item job satisfaction questionnaire and Elena's (1995) fiveitem staff performance questionnaire. The data were analyzed by SPSS software and analyzed by Pearson correlation test, as well as linear regression. The results of the research showed that job satisfaction and employee performance are at a desirable level of reliability. There was no significant difference in job satisfaction with marital variables, sex, history, age, and education. This research showed that there is a positive relationship between job satisfaction and employee performance. In general, the conclusion of the research is that to increase employee performance, managers should pay attention to the job satisfaction of employees.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Conceptual framework refers to a diagrammatical representation that depicts the relationship between a dependent variable and independent variable. In the current research, the conceptual framework presents the relationship between training and employee performance, employee motivation and job-satisfaction in Ghana. More specifically, it portrays that training of employees affects employees' performance, employees' motivation, and job satisfaction in the Parliament of Ghana.

Figure 1: Conceptual framework

Source: Author's own editing

Research designs consist of methods that are used for the collection, measurement, and analysis of the data in line with research objectives. There are different research designs that researchers can adopt to collect, measure, and analyze the data related to study. These include qualitative research designs, quantitative research designs or a mixture of both. However, this study utilized quantitative research design in the form of the survey method. This method was suitable for this study as the researcher did not have any control over the variables and outcomes. It provided an insight into the phenomena in question, and it was flexible in a sense that it helped in identifying the missing part of what is hidden or partially known. This study is built around the methods of training and years of working after going through the training process. Regression, Frequency Distribution Summary and ANOVA methods of analysis were used to ascertain the effects of training on performance, motivation, and job satisfaction of employees/staff of the Parliament of Ghana.

Population is a group of people or objects from which a sample is to be chosen. In the context of the current study, the exact target population consists of a total of 400 employees/staff of the four departments in the Parliament of Ghana.

To examine the relationship between training and employees' performance variables, this paper employed quota sampling technique to draw a sample of 133 employees from a population of 200 employees/staffs in four (4) departments; Research(R), Protocol (P), Human Resource (HR), and ICT (I) in Parliament of Ghana. The sample for the study was determined by using the following formula
$$n = N / (1 + N(e)^2) = 200 / (1 + 200(0.05)^2) = 133$$

Where n is the optimum sample size, $N = 200$ is the target population of all the employees of the four departments in the Parliament of Ghana while e is the probability of error determined as the 0.05 for 95% confidence level.

Validity refers to the extent to which a research instrument measures what it is intended to measure. The validity of the instrument, which is a questionnaire in this case, that was used for data collection was determined by ensuring that all the questions contained in the questionnaire were in line with the study's overall research questions as well as its objectives. The questionnaire was validated through self-filling approach by some respondents to test their understanding and interpretation of the questions to ensure that such questions bear some meaning and the answers provided by those respondents were used to fine-tune the questionnaires.

Reliability is defined as the extent to which the research instrument that is used for data collection in the study demonstrates consistency with the objectives. To ensure reliability of the instrument, the questionnaire was verified by the Heads of the HR Department of the Parliament of Ghana in line with previous scientific research related to the research topic to get better understanding of the methods used.

In line with this, there is a large scale of empirical studies that examine the link between employees' training and employees' performance and/or organizational performance based on various organizations in different countries. Such studies provide empirical evidence in support of the positive correlation between employee training and employees' performance (e.g., Awang et al., 2010; Tahir & Sajjad, 2013; Bataineh, 2014; Dabale, 2014; Nan, 2014; Afsana et al., 2015; Athar & Shah, 2015 and Ugbombhe et al., 2016). This finding is corroborated by a growing concern among most of the government, international organizations, and private sector (including the Parliament of Ghana) employees who claim that their organizations seem not to realize the importance of employee training on employee performance because they generally curtail or squeeze training budgets every year. This situation not only negatively affects employees' performance as employees must always update their skills, knowledge, and competencies to cope

with the ever-changing working environment, uncertain conditions and changes in technology but also demotivates employees, increases job dissatisfaction and job turnover, and consequently increases the costs of hiring new employees with resultant slowdown in organizational profitability. Therefore, the present study seeks to fill the existing research vacuum in the Parliament of Ghana by examining the effect of training on employee performance, motivation, and job satisfaction. This study used primary data collected through self-administered questionnaire consisting of openended questions and closed questions some of which are anchored in providing comprehensive feedback for measurement of various constructs. This allowed the respondents to answer the questions at their own rate and contribute to improving the accuracy of the responses given by the respondents

Research Questions:

- What is the effect of training on employee performance?
- To what extent does training enhance employees' motivation?
- To what extent does training enhance employees' satisfaction?

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To ascertain a precise and accurate measurement and results, all related questions on performance, motivation and job satisfaction in the questionnaire respectively were accumulated to find the average of each dependent variable. In that case, the overall output depicts the nature of the analysis.

TABLE 1: SUMMARY OF RESPONDENTS ON PERFORMANCE, MOTIVATION AND JOB SATISFACTION

Measurement Aspect	Very Poor %	Poor %	Good %	Excellent %	Total %
Performance	1.4	12.3	79.6	6.6	100.0
Motivation	0.0	11.6	79.6	8.9	100.0
Job Satisfaction	1.8	23.6	67.1	7.6	100.0

Source: Author's own editing

Table 1 shows the impact on performance, motivation, and job satisfaction because of training.

Training has a positive impact on performance and motivation which has over 85%; it also has around 75% positive influence on job satisfaction. On this account, training has a higher effect on motivation and performance but a relatively lower effect on job satisfaction. Additionally, Performance and Motivation measurement levels are good with 79.6. Also, performance and motivation were a very poor (%) measurement aspect 1.4, 0.0, respectively, and 1.8 for job satisfaction indicating a good and strong distribution summary. There can be research to find out why there were such low percentages for the three measurement and find the reasons as to why it happened.

Performance, motivation, and job satisfaction were correlated to study the mutual connection and relationship. For example, to what extent would performance and motivation change given the change in job satisfaction level? The results are summarized in the table below.

TABLE 2: CORRELATION COEFFICIENT BETWEEN PERFORMANCE, MOTIVATION AND JOB SATISFACTION

	Performance	Motivation	Job Satisfaction
Performance	1	0.330	0.172
Motivation		1	0.235
Job Satisfaction			1

Source: Author's own editing

From Table 2, the correlation coefficient $r=0.330$ indicates that a positive linear correlation exists between performance and motivation. This linear relationship is moderately strong. The correlation coefficient $r=0.172$ indicates that a positive linear correlation exists between performance and job satisfaction. This linear relationship is weak. The correlation coefficient $r=0.235$ indicates that a positive linear correlation exists between motivation and job satisfaction. This linear relationship is moderately strong. Linear regression was used to determine the effect of each additional year after the training on performance, motivation, and job satisfaction. The results are summarized below.

TABLE 3: REGRESSION: EFFECTS OF TIME DURATION ON PERFORMANCE

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	3.892	0.059		65.836	0.000
How many years (since you had training) have you been working in your department in this organization?	-0.035	0.016	-0.144	-2.175	0.031

a. Dependent Variable: Performance Average
 Source: Author's own computation from SPSS

From Table 3, Staffs who have just been trained or received training are associated with 3.892 performance level. There seem to exist a negative correlation between performance and the time duration after training. Coefficient ($\beta_1 = -0.035$) indicates that any additional year of working after training is associated with 0.035 decrease in performance level. The Regression P-value 0.031 which is less than 0.005 ($0.031 < 0.05$) indicates that the effects of time duration on performance is statistically significant. The results are in the right direction because when staffs are freshly trained; all ideas and working standards are fresh in mind and with that it makes working very easy and, hence increasing productivity. As years gone by, those who have been trained for years needs to be given new standards of training to meet the changing working environment. As there are new technological changes and innovations now and then, training needs to be conducted to those working staffs who have been working in Parliament for long and has since had only training when started working there for first time to maintain or avoid the decrease in the performance level.

LINEAR REGRESSION ON MOTIVATION

Table 4: Regression: Effects of time duration on Motivation Coefficients

Mode 1	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	3.914	0.041		94.572	0.000
How many years (since you had training) have you been working in your department in this organization?	-0.002	0.011	-0.014	-0.211	0.833

a. Dependent Variable: Motivational Average *Source: Author's own computation from SPSS* From Table 4, Staffs who have just been trained or received training are associated with 3.914 motivation level. There seem to exist a negative correlation between motivation and the time duration after training. Coefficient ($\beta_1 = -0.002$) indicates that any additional year of working after training is associated with 0.002 decrease in motivational level. The Regression P-value 0.833 which is greater than 0.005 ($0.833 > 0.05$) indicates that the effects of time duration on motivation are not statistically significant. The results are in the right direction because when staff is freshly trained, all ideas and working standards are fresh in mind and with that it makes working very easy and hence motivates staffs to work more and shows commitments to their work hence increasing productivity and efficiency. As years gone by, those who have been trained for years needs to be given new standards of training in order to meet the changing working environment. As there are new technological changes and innovations now and then, training needs to be conducted to those working staffs who have been working in Parliament for long and has since had only training when started working there for first time to maintain or avoid the decrease in the motivational level.

LINEAR REGRESSION ON JOB SATISFACTION

TABLE 5: REGRESSION: EFFECTS OF TIME DURATION ON JOB SATISFACTION

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	3.689	0.060		60.991	0.000
How many years (since you had training) have you been working in your department in this organization?	9.741E-5	0.016	0.000	0.006	0.995

a. Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction Average *Source:*

Author's own computation from SPSS From table 5, Staff who have just been trained or received training are associated with 3.689 job satisfaction level. There is a positive correlation between job satisfaction and the time duration after training seems to exist. Coefficient ($\beta_1 = 9.74 \times 10^{-5}$) indicates that any additional year of working after training is associated with 9.74×10^{-5} increase in job satisfaction level. The Regression P-value 0.995 which is greater than 0.005 ($0.995 > 0.05$) indicates that the effects of time duration on job satisfaction are not statistically significant. The results are true because when staff is freshly trained, all ideas and working standards are fresh in mind and with that it makes working very easy and staffs are very satisfied with their working environment. As years gone by, those who have been trained for years needs to be given new standards of training to meet the changing working environment. As there are new technological changes and innovations now and then, training needs to be conducted to the working staff who have been working in the Parliament for long and has since had only training when these

started working there for first time to maintain or avoid the decrease in the job satisfaction level. Any little effort made in providing training will help maintain or increase the job satisfaction level hence achieving efficient productivity among the staff in the Parliament of Ghana.

Testing for Equality of means

To run a t-test for equality of means, first test the assumption of equality of variance between the groups Job satisfaction, motivation, and performance. If the test reveals the variances are equal, then run t-test assuming equality of variances. If the test reveals the variances are not equal, then run t-test for assuming unequal variables. There are three ways in determining statistical significance. First, you can compare the t-value to a critical value (CV) in the Table 6. For 195 degree of freedom (df) the critical value (CV) is 1.972 which is same for motivation and satisfaction. The critical value was derived from the t- distribution critical value table. For job satisfaction, the t-value is 1.453 which is smaller than critical value 1.972. For motivation the t-value is 0.235 which is also smaller than the critical value 1.972. For performance the t-value is 3.677 which is larger than the critical value 1.972. When the t-value is larger than the critical value, then the means are statistically significantly different. Secondly, we can use the probability value (P-value) to determine the statistical difference. The P-value for job satisfaction ($0.148 > 0.05$). The P-value for motivation ($0.814 > 0.05$) and the P-value for performance ($0.010 < 0.05$). If the P-value is less than 0.05, then the means are statistically significantly different. Lastly, we can also use the confidence interval to determine the statistical difference. For job satisfaction confidence interval, the lower value is -0.05242 and the upper value is 0.34599 which crosses zero. For motivation confidence interval, the lower value is -0.11842 and the upper value is 0.15054 which includes zero. For performance confidence interval, the lower value is -0.08950 and the upper value is 0.61531 which does not include zero. If the lower and upper value does not cross zero or does not include zero, then the means are statistically significantly different.

In the quest to ascertain the mean effects of ‘on the job training’, coaching and job rotation on job satisfaction, motivation, and performance respectively. It becomes then imperative to run a group descriptive statistic to tell the influences and impacts among the independent and dependent variables. The results are explained below.

TABLE 6: MEAN DIFFERENCES OF SATISFACTION, MOTIVATION AND PERFORMANCE BY ON-THE-JOB TRAINING METHOD (RESULTS OF T-TEST)

Group Statistics

	Which 'On the Job Training' method was used for your training?	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Sig. level (2-tailed test)
Job Satisfaction Average	Coaching	157	3.7176	.55523	0.1480
	Job Rotation	40	3.5708	.62690	0.1820
Motivational Average	Coaching	157	3.9119	.36278	0.8140
	Job Rotation	40	3.8958	.46331	0.8390
Performance Average	Coaching	157	3.8691	.45683	0.0000
	Job Rotation	40	3.5167	.79311	0.0100

Source: Author's own computation from SPSS

HYPOTHESES; TESTING ON AVERAGE PERFORMANCE (COACHING OR JOB ROTATION)

H0: The average performance is equal if the employee received coaching or job rotation. ($\mu_1 = \mu_2$)

H1: The average performance is different if the employee received coaching or job rotation. ($\mu_1 \neq \mu_2$).

Based on the Table 6, P-value ($0.010 < 0.05$) and thus, we reject H0. It means that at 5% significance level, there is not enough evidence to support the claim that the average performance is equal if the employee received coaching or job rotation. Therefore, the two methods are significantly different from each other based on the effects on performance. Also, the means 3.8691 and 3.5167 are significantly different which indicates coaching is significantly different from job rotation on performance. New research can be conducted to find the best suitable methods; however, the feasible and realistic method should be adopted. The chosen method should base on available training facility in the Parliament of Ghana, the method which is quality but cost effective and a method that can be easily applicable and understood by the staff. For easy and smooth operation

coaching can be used since is significantly different from job rotation provided there is available resources and facilities to undergo the training.

HYPOTHESES; TESTING ON AVERAGE MOTIVATION (COACHING OR JOB ROTATION)

H0: The average motivation is equal if the employee received coaching or job rotation. ($\mu_1=\mu_2$)

H1: The average motivation is different if the employee received coaching or job rotation. ($\mu_1\neq\mu_2$).

According to Table 6, the P-value ($0.814>0.05$) and thus, we fail to reject H0. It means that at 5% significance level, there is not enough evidence to support the claim that the average motivation is equal if the employee received coaching or job rotation. Again, the means 3.9119 and 3.8958 are not significantly different which indicates coaching and job rotation are the same on motivation. Any of the methods that is best suitable can be used since the effects are the same. Again, for easy and smooth operation, the one which is very realistic and very accessible should be considered.

HYPOTHESES; TESTING ON AVERAGE JOB SATISFACTION (COACHING OR JOB ROTATION)

H0: The average job satisfaction is equal if the employee received coaching or job rotation. ($\mu_1=\mu_2$)

H1: The average job satisfaction is different if the employee received coaching or job rotation. ($\mu_1\neq\mu_2$).

Table 6 depicts, the P-value ($0.148>0.05$) and thus, we fail to reject H0. It means that at 5% significance level, there is not enough evidence to support the claim that the average job satisfaction is equal if the employee received coaching or job rotation. Additionally, the means 3.7176 and 3.5708 are not significantly different which indicates coaching and job rotation are the same on job satisfaction. Any of the method that is best suitable can be used since the effects are the same. Again, for easy and smooth operation, the one which is very realistic and very accessible should be considered.

To know the precise mean effects on ‘off the job training’, lecture method and vestibule method on job satisfaction, motivation, and performance respectively. It is very important to run a

descriptive statistic to tell the influences and impacts among the independent and dependent variables. The results are explained below.

TABLE 7: MEAN DIFFERENCES OF SATISFACTION, MOTIVATION AND PERFORMANCE BY OFF THE JOB TRAINING METHOD (RESULTS OF T-TEST)

Group Statistics

	Which 'Off the Job Training' method was used for your training?	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Sig. level (2-tailed test)
Job Satisfaction Average	Lecture Method	154	3.7100	0.62180	0.918
	Vestibule Method	41	3.6992	0.47758	0.905
Motivational Average	Lecture Method	154	3.9275	0.38202	0.953
	Vestibule Method	41	3.9634	0.37917	0.592
Performance Average	Lecture Method	154	3.8463	0.56287	0.032
	Vestibule Method	41	3.6260	0.64394	0.051

Source: Author's own computation from SPSS

HYPOTHESES; TESTING ON AVERAGE PERFORMANCE (LECTURE METHOD OR VESTIBULE METHOD)

H0: The average performance is equal if the employee received lecture method or vestibule method. ($\mu_1 = \mu_2$)

H1: The average performance is different if the employee received lecture method or vestibule method. ($\mu_1 \neq \mu_2$).

Based on Table 7, the P-value ($0.032 < 0.05$) and thus, we reject H0. It means that at 5% significance level, there is not enough evidence to support the claim that the average performance is equal if the employee received lecture methods or vestibule methods. Therefore, the two methods are significantly different from each other based on the effects on performance. Also, the means 3.8463 and 3.6260 are significantly different which indicates lecture method is significantly different from vestibule method on performance. Any of the methods that is best suitable can be used since the effects are the same.

Again, for easy and smooth operation lecture method can be used since is significantly different from vestibule method provided there is available resources and facilities to undergo the training. Hence, one which is very realistic and very accessible should be considered.

HYPOTHESES; TESTING ON AVERAGE MOTIVATION (LECTURE METHOD OR VESTIBULE METHOD)

H0: The average motivation is equal if the employee received lecture method or vestibule method. ($\mu_1=\mu_2$)

H1: The average motivation is different if the employee received lecture method or vestibule method. ($\mu_1\neq\mu_2$).

According to Table 7, the P-value ($0.953>0.05$) and thus, we fail to reject H0. It means that at 5% significance level, there is not enough evidence to support the claim that the average motivation is equal if the employee received lecture method or vestibule method. Again, the means 3.9275 and 3.9634 are not significantly different which indicates lecture method and vestibule method are the same on motivation. Any of the methods that is best suitable can be used since the effects are the same. Again, for easy and smooth operation, the one which is very realistic and very accessible should be considered.

HYPOTHESES; TESTING ON AVERAGE JOB SATISFACTION (LECTURE METHOD OR VESTIBULE METHOD)

H0: The average job satisfaction is equal if the employee received lecture method or vestibule method. ($\mu_1=\mu_2$)

H1: The average job satisfaction is different if the employee received lecture method or vestibule method. ($\mu_1\neq\mu_2$).

Table 7 depicts the P-value ($0.918>0.05$) and thus, we fail to reject H0. It means that at 5% significance level, there is not enough evidence to support the claim that the average job satisfaction is equal if the employee received lecture method and vestibule method. Additionally, the means 3.7100 and 3.6992 are not significantly different which indicates lecture method and vestibule

methods are the same on job satisfaction. Any of the method that is best suitable can be used since the effects are the same. Again, for easy and smooth operation, the one which is very realistic and very accessible should be considered.

CONCLUSIONS

The importance of training in the corporate world has been widely discussed in literatures and there is a large body of the theoretical and empirical literature which provides empirical evidence in support of either direct or indirect link between training and employees' performance, motivation, and job satisfaction with resultant positive spillovers on organizational performance. This is because the success and failure of any organization to achieve its objectives depends highly on training of its workforce. Therefore, top management within organizations should realize the importance of investing in employees' training for the sake of improving their performance and hence that of an organization. Nevertheless, some organizations (including the Parliament of Ghana) in Ghana seem not to recognize this importance because they continue to underrate and overlook the ramification of training and this situation incapacitates employees, lowers performance, demotivates them, increases job turnover and the costs of hiring new employees, which consequently reduces the organizational profitability. Thus, this paper examined the impact of training on employee's performance, employee's motivation, and job satisfaction in the context of the staffs in the Parliament of Ghana not only with a view to fill existing research gap in the Parliament of Ghana staffs but also to convince policymakers and managers in various departments in the parliament of Ghana about the value of training on employee's performance employees' motivation and job-satisfaction. The findings of this research shows that training plays a central role in improving employee performance, raising employee motivation, and maximizing job satisfaction. Finally, the Parliamentary Service Board should concentrate more on the training methods with feasible and realistic schedule for staff to regularly organize annual training sessions among staff to get themselves acquainted with the new training methods and ideas to sharpen the employees' skills, knowledge, and abilities to capacitate them to cope with the ever-changing working environment and uncertain conditions and improve their performance, motivation, and job satisfaction.

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